

Artificial Intelligence in Human Resource Management-A Review of Opportunities and Challenges

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Abstract

Digitalization has influenced and is influencing our education, occupation, lifestyle, achievements, possessions, relations, beliefs, and perception of life. The biggest workplace disruptor is next-generation digital technologies. The dynamic nature of digitalization is itself a challenge to the organization as a whole and particularly human resource management since employees are the most valuable assets in an organization. To create a modern organization digitalization will be required at all connected levels. The motivation of the study is to analyze and determine the opportunities and challenges of AI in HRM in the Indian context. Organizations that do not adopt newer technologies will find it difficult to survive.

Since digital technology will result in both direct and indirect implications of the employees and the organization, it has to be studied. A detailed survey of existing literature on the context was studied thoroughly. The findings of the study will give a deeper understanding of the implications of digital technology for HR Managers and all the stakeholders concerned.

Keywords: Human Resource Information Systems, HRIS, Automation in HR.

Introduction

The improvement in technology is making the dynamic capabilities of AI scale new horizons and is impacting the way business are been conducted. The individual usage of digital products is high, but the knowledge and usage in terms of the technological capabilities of AI in HRM is low. This kind of technology, is has more potential than HRIS (Human resource information system), will change and shift the older practices of handling human resources in an organization.

AI is impacting the Human resource planning chain right from the start, such as recruitment, selecting, hiring, training, induction, training, evaluation, promotion, layoff, remuneration, performance management, and employee relations.

The topic “Artificial intelligence for human resource management - opportunities and challenges” will give a new direction to the businesses and HR managers in decision making.

Artificial intelligence will progressively supplement all manual work works (Coster and Westelius, 2016). Intelligent computers, for example, AI (Artificial intelligence), will likewise claim stake over routine duties (Makridakis, 2017). More and more machines

are detectable easily because they are always connected to the internet and consequently send status data (Ebersold and Glass, 2015). Connected cars, homes are such instances how digitization appears to the public eye. According to Anderson 2017, everything will be modified to digital in the future. These do not just change how we convey and communicate as people, the way we associate with other people in work, which infers enormous changes for any HR administrator (Larkin, 2017).

Literature Review

Palmer et.al.,(2017) give insights on how digitalization will impact the domain of HRM. The software developer Adobe chose to quit selling its items in physical bundles and turned into a cloud-based programming supplier in 2011 (Smedley, 2014). For clients, this implied downloading or pursuing a month to month membership as opposed to accepting a CD. For the representatives then again, this brought about better approaches for working and subsequently understood a new job for the HR. Although not previously observed HRM needed to change because of its cloud-based methodology and guide the representatives in their approaches for working. The HRM turned out to be progressively changing and more individuals required with new knowledge occupied work. Moreover, the HRM experts needed to change, how surveys are done, forsaking the yearly audit for persistent and prompt input through new frameworks and workshops (Palmer et al., 2017; Smedley, 2014). If a new organization has to grow in this digital change HR experts, need to change their views on the impact of digitalization and understand its importance.

Evolution of HRM

HR managers, to understand the implications of digitalization, have understood the evolution and the meaning of HRM. Watson (2009), defines human resources as “the efforts, knowledge, capabilities and committed behaviors which people contribute to a work organization as part of an employment exchange.” Further, HRM can explain as the “managing of human resources in order to enable the organization to develop” (Watson, 2009). Moreover, Bredin and Soderlund (2006) explain HRM as “practices concerning the management of the relationship between the employees and the organization in which they work.”

McKinsey Global Institute proposes that 56 percent of the usual contract undertakings could be robotized with current advances and constrained procedural changes. Its utilization of programming with AI and AI capabilities to deal with repeatable jobs that people have customarily performed is now changing the face of HR administrations. The outcome: Processing time fell 66 percent, consistency improved and, four full-time representatives moved to more higher positions. Given the minimal effort of bots, the business case for robotization is clear – and the administration effect is similarly evident. The quantifiable consequence and quicker turnaround time are probably going to improve employment rates. Digitalization’s potential efficiency worth is justifiable.

Evolution of e-HRM

Definition: According to Lippert & Michael Swiercz, 2005 “AI in HR is a course of action for gathering, putting away, keeping up, recovering and approving information required by to know about its people, work force exercises, and association unit qualities.”

Denise, 2017 reports that Delta corp technology with AI programming to select required candidates, with a 71% decrease in enlistment costs and a triple increment in enrollment effectiveness.

Hutson, 2017 observed that AI has the characteristics of screening candidates without prejudice.

Jain & Li, 2011 apprehend that face recognition techniques can be used in the exam to determine if the candidate is consistent with the document, thereby preventing others from taking the test instead of the candidate who has applied.

Otley, 1999 reports that 360-degree performance evaluation methods using machines can be used automatically and quickly.

Verne, 2018 studied IBM HR functions and found out that AI is helping the division with various capacities, including estimating worker skill, increasing commitment, upgrading representative training, alter and configuration work orders, and gaining new, assorted ability.

Case 1: Unilever is drastically changing its selection procedure. The organization is exploring different avenues regarding – in addition to other things – internet life, web based games, and AI to additionally digitalize how they are enrolling.

Case 2: Cisco sorts out hackathons to fabricate new HR items – for example, the YouBelong@ Cisco application and Ask Alex. The previous is intended to support new contracts and their directors during their onboarding period and the last is a voice order application that offers fast responses to different HR inquiries regarding occasion arrangement, costs, and so forth.

Case 3: IBM launched a digital learning platform that gives its employees a fully customized experience. The human resource management system provided by IBM is called IBM Watson. It has three modules that are assisted by AI namely, talent assessment, acquisition, and development. IBM Watson chats with potential candidates and accesses the job fit with the organization requirement. IBM Watson also identifies the skills required for various industries and also prepares interview questions(IBM, 2018).

The future of HR 2019: In the Know or the No compiled by KPMG offers insights on how AI is transforming HR practices. The report says that only 39% of the people leading the HR department are confident in transforming the workforce into a new AI-capable workforce. About two-thirds of the managers surveyed understood that HR is undergoing a digital transformation and, only 40% have a plan ready for this transformation. 41% of the respondents said that workplace culture is the main barrier to digital transformation. 88 % observes that the investment made in AI is worthwhile.

Objectives

A key component in the managing of the implications of digitalization is HRM understands the human nature of the problem that is dealt. Digitalization demands HRM to evolve, as it requires new HR competencies, new employment forms, and agile HR processes.

Consequently, the objective of the study will be to delve deeper into HRM in a digital era. More specifically, the aim is to get a deeper understanding of how digitalization has implications for HR managers.

Through literature reviews, the study will analyze the current status, perception of HR managers about the implications of digitalization. Answers will be looked for the accompanying inquiries like

1. How are HRM processes changing as a result of digitalization?
2. What are the new capabilities required within the HR team?
3. How is HRM, preparing within their organizations, for all these changes?

Research Methodology

Extensive secondary data was collected from the available literature. Mostly the surveys conducted by global research institutions were studied. Cases were studied in detail about the impact of AI in HR functions. Surveys already conducted were also incorporated in the study.

Future Study and Practical Implications

The future pattern of the AI for HRM is as yet the cooperation of human and machine with the presence of confliction. The McKinsey Global Institute accepts that “over 30% of exercises in 60%

of occupations can be supplanted by man-made consciousness” (Chui and Francisco, 2017). As per an examination report from the University of Oxford, in the following 10 to 20 years, half of the 702 occupations in the United States will vanish affected by IT, and about 47% of US workers will be utilized. In light of these information, how to hoist the aggressive insight of human asset administrators and send HR proficiently might be hard to deal with.

The most effective method to work together with the human and machine utilizing creating advancements is additionally a significant inquiry. The enormous scale ascend in joblessness rate additionally will cause restriction and opposition. In detail, in each element of human asset the board, there is commendable looking into inquiries to be replied. For instance, the procedure plan for the coordinating between work searchers and suppliers dependent on the HR model and AI. The shrewd exhibition assessment framework joined with the AI calculations and execution assessment models (Dom, 2018).

Conclusion

In conclusion, the effects of information systems in human resources are not understood by the HR Managers and the impact of Information systems on the organization as a whole. But they do understand that artificial intelligence will have far-reaching consequences in the future. Thus understanding the future implications of Information systems in the Human resource department is becoming very vital for the success of the organizations.

We further conclude that AI in HRM can be used with data mining in decision support systems. The recruitment process in the future will have face recognition systems, natural language processing and will form a very robust decision support system. AI will assist in training and development and even with performance evaluation.

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